

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 10

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 10

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>¹ Why do You stand afar off, O LORD? Why do You hide <i>Yourself</i> in times of trouble?</p>	<p>לָמָּה יְהוָה תִּעְמָד בְּרָחֹק תִּעְלִים לְעֵתוֹת בְּצָרָה: ² בְּגִאֲוֹת רָשָׁע</p>
<p>² In pride the wicked hotly pursue the afflicted; Let them be caught in the plots which they have devised.</p>	<p>יִדְלַק עָנִי יִתְפָּשׂוּ אֲבִמְזֻמֹּת זֵו תִּשָּׁבוּ: ³ כִּי־הִלֵּל רָשָׁע עַל־תַּאֲוֹת</p>
<p>³ For the wicked boasts of his heart's desire, And the greedy man curses <i>and</i> spurns the LORD.</p>	<p>נִפְשָׁו וּבִצְעַ בְּרוּךְ נַאֲץ אִיהוָה: ⁴ רָשָׁע כְּגִבְהַ אָפוּ בַל־יִדְרֹשׁ אֵין</p>
<p>⁴ The wicked, in the haughtiness of his countenance, does not seek <i>Him</i>. All his thoughts are, "There is no God."</p>	<p>אֱלֹהִים כָּל־מְזֻמֹּתָיו: ⁵ יִתְחַלּוּ דַרְכּוֹ [דַרְכָיו] בְּכָל־עֵת מְרוֹם</p>
<p>⁵ His ways prosper at all times; Your judgments are on high, out of his sight; As for all his adversaries, he snorts at them.</p>	<p>מִשְׁפָּטֶיךָ מִנִּגְדּוֹ כָּל־צֹרְרָיו יִפִּית בָּהֶם: ⁶ אָמַר בְּלִבּוֹ בַל־אֶמוּט לִדְר וְדָר אֲשֶׁר לֹא־בָרַע: ⁷ אֵלֶּה</p>
<p>⁶ He says to himself, "I will not be moved; Throughout all generations I will not be in adversity."</p>	<p>פִּיהוּ מְלֵא וּמְרֻמֹּת וְתֹךְ תַּחַת לְשׁוֹנוֹ עָמַל וְאָוֶן: ⁸ יִשָּׁב אֲבִמְאָרֵב</p>
<p>⁷ His mouth is full of curses and deceit and oppression; Under his tongue is mischief and wickedness.</p>	<p>תְּחַזְרִים בְּמִסְתָּרִים יִתְרַג נֶקְי עֵינָיו לְחִלְקָה יִצְפְּנוּ: ⁹ יֵאָרֵב בְּמִסְתָּר אֲ</p>
<p>⁸ He sits in the lurking places of the villages; In the hiding places he kills the innocent; His eyes stealthily watch for the unfortunate.</p>	<p>כְּאֲרִיֶּה בְסִכְּהַ יֵאָרֵב לְחַטּוֹף עָנִי יִחַטֵּף עָנִי בְמִשְׁכּוֹ בְרִשְׁתּוֹ: ¹⁰ וְדָכָה [יִדְכָה] יִשָּׁח וְנָפַל בְּעֲצוּמָיו</p>
<p>⁹ He lurks in a hiding place as a lion in his lair; He lurks to catch the afflicted; He catches the afflicted when he draws him into his net.</p>	<p>תְּלַכְּאִים [תִּיל] [כְּאִים]: ¹¹ אָמַר בְּלִבּוֹ שָׁכַח אֵל הַסְּתִיר כְּפָנָיו בַּל־ רָאָה לְנִצָּחַת: ¹² קוֹמָה יְהוָה אֵל</p>
<p>¹⁰ He crouches, he bows down, And the unfortunate fall by his mighty ones.</p>	<p>נִשְׂא יָדָךְ אֵל־תִּשְׁכַּח עֲנִיִּים [עֲנִיִּים]: ¹³ עַל־מָה אֲנֹאץ רָשָׁע אֲ</p>
<p>¹¹ He says to himself, "God has forgotten; He has hidden His face; He will never see it."</p>	<p>אֱלֹהִים אָמַר בְּלִבּוֹ לֹא תִדְרֹשׁ: ¹⁴ רְאֵתָה כִּי־אֵתָה אֲעֲמֵל וְכַעַס אֲ</p>
<p>¹² Arise, O LORD; O God, lift up Your hand. Do not forget the afflicted.</p>	<p></p>

¹³ Why has the wicked spurned God? He has said to himself, "You will not require *it*."

¹⁴ You have seen *it*, for You have beheld mischief and vexation to take it into Your hand. The unfortunate commits *himself* to You; You have been the helper of the orphan.

¹⁵ Break the arm of the wicked and the evildoer, Seek out his wickedness until You find none.

¹⁶ The LORD is King forever and ever; Nations have perished from His land.

¹⁷ O LORD, You have heard the desire of the humble; You will strengthen their heart, You will incline Your ear

¹⁸ To vindicate the orphan and the oppressed, So that man who is of the earth will no longer cause terror.

תִּבְיֹט לְתֹת בְּיָדְךָ עָלֶיךָ יַעֲזֹב
חֲלָכָה יִתּוֹם אֶתָּה אֱהִיֶת עֹזֶר : ¹⁵
שָׁבַר זְרוּעַ רָשָׁע וְרָע תִּדְרוֹשׁ
רָשָׁעוֹ בַל־תִּמְצָא : ¹⁶ יִהְיֶה מִלֶּךְ
עוֹלָם וְעַד אֲבָדוּ גֹוִים מֵאֶרֶץ : ¹⁷
תִּשְׁמַע עֲנָוִים שְׁמַעַת יְהוָה תִּכְיֶן
לִבָּם תִּקְשִׁיב אָזְנוֹךָ : ¹⁸ לְשַׁפֵּט יִתּוֹם
וְרָךְ בַּל־יֹוֹסִיף עוֹד לַעֲרֹץ אָנוּשׁ
מִן־הָאָרֶץ :

Targum

Psa. 10:1 Why, O LORD, will you stand afar off, hide yourself in the dwelling of the holy ones in the times of distress? ² In brutality the wicked man will pursue the poor man; they will be caught in the scheme that they plotted to carry out. ³ For the wicked man is praised for the craving of his soul; he who blesses the violent man abhors the word of the LORD. ⁴ The wicked man in the grossness of his spirit will not seek God, and he will say in his heart that his thoughts are not manifest in the presence of the LORD. ⁵ His ways prosper at all times; your judgments are far from his sight; he will rebuke all his oppressors. ⁶ He will say in his heart, "I will not be shaken from doing evil for all generations." ⁷ His mouth is curses, full of guile and deceit; under his tongue is misery and falsehood. ⁸ He will sit in the hiding places of the courtyards; in secret places he will kill the innocent; he will hide his eyes against the poor. ⁹ He will lie in wait in secret places like a lion in his covert; he will lie in wait to seize the poor man; he will seize the poor man when he is drawn into his trap. ¹⁰ The poor man will be crushed, and sink down, and he will fall into the power of his hiding places. ¹¹ He will say in his heart, "God has forgotten, he has hidden his face, he does not see forever." ¹² Arise, O LORD, fulfill the oath of your hand, do not forget the humble. ¹³ Why has the wicked man abhorred God? He will say in his heart, "It will not be sought after." ¹⁴ It is manifest in your presence, because you will inflict misery and wrath upon the wicked man; look carefully to pay a good reward to the righteous by your hand; the poor will place their hope on you; you have been a helper to the orphan. ¹⁵ Break the arm of the wicked; and let the evil seek their wickedness, [and] not find it. ¹⁶ The LORD is king forever and ever; the Gentiles have perished from his land. ¹⁷ The desire of the humble is heard in your presence, O LORD; strengthen their heart, incline your ear. ¹⁸ To judge the orphan and poor man; may the sons of men not again be shattered before the wicked of the earth. --

Interlinear

Psa. 10:1		Why	do	You	stand		
Key					H5975		
Lex					עָמַד		
PrtSpeech					Verb		
afar	off	O	Lord	Why	do	You	hide
H7350			H3068				H5956
רְחֹק			יְהוָה				עָלַם
Adj.			Noun				Verb
Yourself	in	times	of	trouble			
		H6256		H6869a			
		עֵת		צָרָה			--
		Noun					
Psa. 10:2		In	pride	the	wicked		
Key			H1346		H7563		
Lex			גִּבְוָה		רָשָׁע		
PrtSpeech			Noun		Adj.		
hotly	pursue	the	afflicted	Let	them	be	
H1814	H1814		H6041				
דָּלַק	דָּלַק		עָנִי				
Verb	Verb		Adj.				
caught	in	the	plots	which	they	have	devised
H8610			H4209	H2098			H2803
תָּפַשׁ			מִזְמָה	זוֹ			תָּשַׁב
Verb			Noun	Part.			Verb
Psa. 10:3		For	the	wicked			
Key				H7563			
Lex				רָשָׁע			
PrtSpeech				Adj.			
boasts	of	his	heart's	desire	And	the	greedy
H1984b			H5315	H8378			H1214
הִלָּל			לִבִּי	תַּאֲוָה			בָּצַע
Verb			Noun	Noun			Verb
man	curses	and	spurns	the	Lord		
H1214	H1288		H5006		H3068		

בָּצַע Verb	בָּרַךְ Verb	נָאץ Verb	יהוה Noun				
Psa. 10:4 Key Lex PrtSpeech	The	wicked H7563 רָשָׁע Adj.	in the	haughtiness H1363 גִּבְהָ Noun	of		
his	countenance H0639 אַף Noun	does	not	seek H1875 דָּרַשׁ Verb	Him		
All H3605 כָּל Noun	his	thoughts H4209 מַזְמֵנָה Noun	are	There H0369 אֵין Part.	is	no H0369 אֵין Part.	God H0430 אֱלֹהִים Noun
Psa. 10:5 Key Lex PrtSpeech		His	ways H1870 דְּרָךְ Noun				
prosper H2342b חוּל --	at	all H3605 כָּל Noun	times H6256 עֵת Noun	Your	judgments H4941 מִשְׁפָּט Noun	are	
on	high H4791 מְרוֹם Noun	out of	his	sight H5048 נֶגַד Part.	As	for	
all H3605 כָּל Noun	his	adversaries H6887c צָרָר Verb	he	snorts H6315 פִּוֵּת Verb	at	them	
Psa. 10:6 Key Lex PrtSpeech	He	says H0559 אָמַר Verb	to	himself H3820 לָב Noun			

I will not be moved Throughout
 H4131
 מוֹט
 Verb

all generations I will not be in adversity
 H1755 H1755 H7451b
 דֹּר דֹּר רָע
 Noun Noun Adj.

Psa. 10:7 His mouth is full of curses and
 Key H6310 H4390 H0423
 Lex פֶּה מָלֵא אָלָה
 PrtSpeech Noun Verb Noun

deceit and oppression Under his
 H4820 H8496 H8478
 מְרִמָּה תִּדְּתַח אָנּוֹן
 Noun Noun Part.

tongue is mischief and wickedness
 H3956 H5999 H0205
 לְשׁוֹן עֲמָל אָוֶן
 Noun Noun Noun

Psa. 10:8 He sits in the lurking places of
 Key H3427 H3993 H3993
 Lex יָשָׁב מְאָרָב מְאָרָב
 PrtSpeech Verb Noun Noun

the villages In the hiding places he kills the
 H2691b H4565 H4565 H2026
 קְצָר מְסֻתָּר מְסֻתָּר הָרַג
 Noun Noun Noun Noun Verb

innocent His eyes stealthily watch for the
 H5355a H5869 H6845 H6845
 נָקִי עֵינַי צָפַן צָפַן
 Adj. Noun Verb Verb

unfortunate
 H2489
 חֲלָכָה

H0410		H7911		H5641
אֵל		שָׁכַח		סָתַר
Noun		Verb		Verb

face	He	will	never	see	it
H6440				H7200	
פָּנִים				רָאָה	
Noun				Verb	

Psa. 10:12	Arise	O
Key	H6965	
Lex	קוּם	
PrtSpeech	Verb	

Lord	O	God	lift	up	Your	hand
H3068		H0410	H5375			H3027
יְהוָה		אֵל	נָשָׂא			יָד
Noun		Noun	Verb			Noun

Do	not	forget	the	afflicted
		H7911		H6035
		שָׁכַח		עָנִי
		Verb		Adj.

Psa. 10:13	Why	has	the	wicked
Key				H7563
Lex				רָשָׁע
PrtSpeech				Adj.

spurned	God	He	has	said	to	himself
H5006	H0430			H0559		H3820
נָאץ	אֱלֹהִים			אָמַר		לָב
Verb	Noun			Verb		Noun

You	will	not	require	it
			H1875	
			דָּרַשׁ	
			Verb	

Psa. 10:14	You	have	seen	it	for	You	have	beheld
Key			H7200					H5027
Lex			רָאָה					נָבַט
PrtSpeech			Verb					Verb

mischief	and	vexation	to	take	it	into	Your	hand
H5999		H3708a		H5414				H3027
עָמָל		כָּעַם		נָתַן				יָד
Noun		Noun		Verb				Noun

The	unfortunate	commits	himself	to	You	You	have
	H2489	H5800a					
	חֵלְכָה	עָזַב					
	Noun	Verb					

been	the	helper	of	the	orphan
H1961		H5826			H3490
הָיָה		עָזַר			יָתוֹם
Verb		Verb			Noun

Psa. 10:15	Break	the	arm	of
Key	H7665		H2220	
Lex	שָׁבַר		זָרַע	
PrtSpeech	Verb		Noun	

the	wicked	and	the	evildoer	Seek
	H7563			H7451a	H1875
	רָשָׁע			רָע	דָּרַשׁ
	Adj.			Adj.	Verb

out	his	wickedness	until	You	find	none
		H7562			H4672	H1077
		רָשָׁע			מָצָא	בֵּל
		Noun			Verb	Part.

Psa. 10:16	The	Lord	is	King
Key		H3068		H4428
Lex		יְהוָה		מְלִיךָ
PrtSpeech		Noun		Noun

forever	and	ever	Nations	have	perished
H5769		H5703	H1471		H0006
עוֹלָם		עַד	גוֹי		אָבַד
Noun		Noun	Noun		Verb

from	His	land
		H0776

אָרֶץ
Noun

Psa. 10:17 Key Lex PrtSpeech	O	Lord H3068 יהוה Noun	You	have	heard H8085 שָׁמַע Verb	the		
desire H8378 תַּאֲוָה Noun	of	the H6035 עָנָו Adj.	You	will	strengthen H3559 כִּיָּן Verb	their		
heart H3820 לֵב Noun	You	will	incline H7181 קָשַׁב Verb	Your	ear H0241 אָזֵן Noun			
Psa. 10:18 Key Lex PrtSpeech	To	vindicate H8199 שָׁפַט Verb	the	orphan H3490 יָתוּם Noun	and	the		
oppressed H1790 דָּבַד Adj.	So	that	man H0582 אָנוּשׁ Noun	who	is	of	the H0776 אָרֶץ Noun	earth will
no H1077 בֶּל Part.	longer	cause H6206 עָרַץ Verb	terror H6206 עָרַץ Verb					

Verse One

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>¹ Why do You stand afar off, O LORD? Why do You hide <i>Yourself</i> in times of trouble?</p>	<p>לָמָּה יִתְּנָה פְּעַמֵּי בְּרָחוֹק פְּעָלָיִם לְעֵתוֹת בְּצָרָה :</p>

Verse Analysis

Psalm 10 discusses human relationships. In particular, it addresses the thinking of an individual who has thrown off the yoke of moral and ethical laws. It is hoped that the LORD will break the unchecked power to a point where they cannot hurt anyone else. The people felt that the LORD was far away when the ordinary people suffered.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

Why, in times of trouble, does it seem that you are not with me?

Verse Two

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>² In pride the wicked hotly pursue the afflicted; Let them be caught in the plots which they have devised.</p>	<p>בְּגִאוֹת רָשָׁע יִדְלַק עֲנִי יִתְפָּשׂוּ² : בְּמִזְמוֹת זֵו תִּשָּׁבוּ :</p>

Verse Analysis

In general, a person who is dependent upon another for his existence becomes submissive to that person's will. It is pride and arrogance which causes a person not to bow down to a "higher" power. When a person disobeys the LORD, he is arrogant because the LORD is far more powerful. The human ego tends to do this. Pride opens the soul to Evil inclination.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

May the LORD place the oppression of the oppressor on the oppressor.

Verse Three

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
³ For the wicked boasts of his heart's desire, And the greedy man curses <i>and</i> spurns the LORD.	כִּי־הִלֵּל רָשָׁע עַל־תְּאוֹנֹת נַפְשׁוֹ וּבִצֵּעַ אֵרֶךְ נַאֲץ אֶת־יְהוָה

Verse Analysis

The wicked and greedy see their material possession as something that he has won on their own. The people who believe in the LORD know that what they have materially is a blessing granted to them by the LORD.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

The wicked and greedy boast that all he possesses were because of his abilities.

Verse Four

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
4 The wicked, in the haughtiness of his countenance, does not seek <i>Him</i> . All his thoughts are, "There is no God."	רָשָׁע כְּגִבַּת אָפוֹ בַּל-יִדְרֹשׁ אֵין אֱלֹהִים כָּל-מְזֻמֹּתָיו :

Verse Analysis

אָפוֹ (afo) – means "nose." It can also mean "anger." If one holds his countenance high above all others, he holds their nose above other people. Such people do not believe that the LORD exists.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

People who do not believe in the LORD do not seek Him.

Verse Five

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>⁵ His ways prosper at all times; Your judgments are on high, out of his sight; As for all his adversaries, he snorts at them.</p>	<p>יִתְיַלּוּ דַרְכּוֹ [דַרְכָיו] בְּכָל-עֵת ⁵ מָרוֹם מִשְׁפָּטֶיךָ מִנְגִּדוֹ כָּל-צוֹרְרָיו יִבִּית בָּהֶם :</p>

Verse Analysis

This verse describes a person who does not fear justice from the LORD. Why? Because everything that he does is prosperous materialistically. This type of person does not understand that there is a spiritual world. When his time in Malkhut is over, he does not understand that the soul will enter the spiritual world of Yesod.

An evil person who cheats and steals gains materialistic property but sacrifices their soul.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

An evil person prospers all the time. The LORD's judgment is unknown to him.

Verse Six

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
6 He says to himself, "I will not be moved; Throughout all generations I will not be in adversity."	אָמַר בְּלִבּוֹ בְּלִ-אַמּוֹט לְדָר וְדָר אֲשֶׁר לֹא-בָרַע

Verse Analysis

Even in bad times or misfortunes, the wicked still thrive.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

He says to himself, "No matter what bad times or misfortunes come, the wicked still thrive."

Verse Seven

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
7 His mouth is full of curses and deceit and oppression; Under his tongue is mischief and wickedness.	אֱלֹהֵי פִּיהוּ מְלֵא וּמְרִמּוֹת וְתֵדָר תַּחַת לְשׁוֹנוֹ עֲמָל וְאַוֵּן :

Verse Analysis

אֱלֹהֵי (ala) – means "to swear." This word is used when a person swears or curses against the LORD. This verse says that this person may say righteous things, which is on the tip of his tongue, but the truth is that he remains evil. When a wicked person wants to deceive, he will create an oath that he has no intention to fulfill.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

His mouth is full of oaths and behind these false oaths is his wickedness.

Verse Eight

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>⁸ He sits in the lurking places of the villages; In the hiding places he kills the innocent; His eyes stealthily watch for the unfortunate.</p>	<p>יֵשֵׁב בְּמַאֲרָב תְּצַרִים ⁸ : בְּמִסְתָּרִים יִהְרֹג נַקִּי עֵינָיו לְחַלְכָּה יִצְפֹּנוּ</p>

Verse Analysis

"He sits in the lurking places of the villages" means to make oneself at home in domestic circles and to become well-acquainted with the most intimate affairs of families utilizing social intercourse with the inhabitants of the neighborhood.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

He becomes accepted by the families of a village but then kills the innocent and is watching to take advantage of the weak.

Verse Nine

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
9 He lurks in a hiding place as a lion in his lair; He lurks to catch the afflicted; He catches the afflicted when he draws him into his net.	יֹאֲרֵב בַּמְסֻקָּר אֶכְאֲרֶיהָ בְּסֻכָּה 9 יֹאֲרֵב לַחֲטוּף עֲנִי יַחֲטֵף עֲנִי בְּמִשְׁכוֹ בְּרִשְׁתּוֹ

Verse Analysis

בְּסֻכָּה - (b'sookoo) means "in his lair." This word is actually written in the feminine form. However, the Masoretic point system is being violated in this verse. The wrong point has been placed on the "cuf." This indicates that the author wanted to express that this male person was hiding his real strength by acting like a woman. Since women are weaker than men, this interpretation is valid. The person who is hiding is preparing to attack the poor and abuse them.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

He lies in wait, looking like a weak and peaceful lion; when he can, he will ensnare a poor person to abuse and rob him.

Verse Ten

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>¹⁰ He crouches, he bows down, And the unfortunate fall by his mighty ones.</p>	<p>וְדָכָה [וְדָכָה] יִשָּׁתּוּ וְנִפְּלָ¹⁰ בְּעֲצוּמָיו תִּלְכָּתוּם [תִּלְ] [כָּאִים :]</p>

Verse Analysis

The person who preys on the poor is considered wicked and a low person morally. A lowly person bows down to a mightier person.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

He acts as a humble man; he walks bowed down until the hosts of the weak fall victim to his ways of violence.

Verse Eleven

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
11 He says to himself, "God has forgotten; He has hidden His face; He will never see it."	אָמַר בְּלִבּוֹ שָׁכַח אֱלֹהֵי הַסִּתִּיר פְּנָיו בְּלִרְאָתָהּ לִנְצַחַת :

Verse Analysis

This verse says that the refusal to believe in the LORD's providence in historical events is what the wicked believe. They also believe that the LORD does not see what they are doing. Thus, at the Tikkun, they will not be judged for their evil while on the Earth. They would not believe in a final judgment.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

He says to himself, "The LORD will never see our evil because I do not believe in His existence."

Verse Twelve

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>¹² Arise, O LORD; O God, lift up Your hand. Do not forget the afflicted.</p>	<p>קוֹמָה יְהוָה אֱלֹהֵי נַשְׂא יְדָךְ אֵל- תִּשְׁכַּח עֲנִיִּים [עֲנִיִּים:]</p>

Verse Analysis

The Psalmist is asking the LORD to defend the afflicted and the poor.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

Arise LORD and by your Hand help the afflicted.

Verse Thirteen and Fourteen

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>¹³ Why has the wicked spurned God? He has said to himself, "You will not require <i>it</i>." ¹⁴ You have seen <i>it</i>, for You have beheld mischief and vexation to take it into Your hand. The unfortunate commits <i>himself</i> to You; You have been the helper of the orphan.</p>	<p>עַל־מָה אֲנֹכִי רָשָׁע אֱלֹהִים אָמַר רָאִתָּה כִּי־¹⁴בְּלִבִּי לֹא תִדְרֹשׁ׃ אַתָּה אֲעֲמֵל וְכַעַס אֶתְּבִיט לְתֶת בְּיָדְךָ עֲלִיךָ יְעֻזֵּב</p>

Verse Analysis

The lawless man mocks the LORD by disobeying His Law and thinks that the LORD is not concerned about humankind.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

V.13 – Why does the wicked person mock the LORD? He says in his heart, "The LORD does not care about us."

V. 14 – But You have seen this lawlessness; all things are in Your hands; You have been the helper of the orphan.

Verse Fifteen

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
15 Break the arm of the wicked and the evildoer, Seek out his wickedness until You find none.	שִׁבְרֵ זְרוּעַ רָשָׁע וְזָרַע תְּדַרְוֶנּוּ- רָשָׁעוֹ בְּלֹ-תִמְצָא :

Verse Analysis

The Psalmist asked the LORD to seek out evil and punish it. When this is complete evil will be banished from the Earth.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

LORD, remove the wicked from the Earth so that You will not find it here anymore.

Verse Sixteen

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
16 The LORD is King forever and ever; Nations have perished from His land.	יְהוָה מֶלֶךְ עוֹלָם וָעֶד אֲבָדוּ גוֹיִם מֵאֶרֶץ

Verse Analysis

One day the LORD's sovereignty will be acknowledged everywhere.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

The LORD is King forever; however, the nations of the Earth will one day perish.

Verse Seventeen

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>¹⁷ O LORD, You have heard the desire of the humble; You will strengthen their heart, You will incline Your ear</p>	<p>תְּאַזְחַת עֲנָנִים שְׁמַעַת יְהוָה תְּכִיֵן לִבָּם תִּקְשִׁיב אָזְנְךָ :</p>

Verse Analysis

The LORD has always heard the voice of the humble and poor. LORD, you can strengthen the humble.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

LORD, You have heard the desire of the humble; now guide their hearts and hear their cries for help.

Verse Eighteen

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>¹⁸ To vindicate the orphan and the oppressed, So that man who is of the earth will no longer cause terror.</p>	<p>לְשַׁפֵּט יְתוּם וְאֶרְבָּךְ בֶּן-יֹסֵיף עוֹד לְעֵרֹץ אֲנֹשׁ מִן-הָאָרֶץ :</p>

Verse Analysis

The LORD always champions the orphan and poor.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

Champion the orphans and the oppressed so that the men of violence will not continue to spread their terror around the Earth.

Complete Psalm Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

Why, in times of trouble, does it seem that you are not with me?

May the LORD place the oppression of the oppressor on the oppressor.

The wicked and greedy boast that all he possesses were because of his abilities.

People who do not believe in the LORD do not seek Him.

An evil person prospers all the time. The LORD's judgment is unknown to him.

He says to himself, "No matter what bad times or misfortunes come, the wicked still thrive."

His mouth is full of oaths and behind these false oaths is his wickedness.

He becomes accepted by the families of a village but then kills the innocent and is watching to take advantage of the weak.

He lies in wait, looking like a weak and peaceful lion; when he can, he will ensnare a poor person to abuse and rob him.

He acts as a humble man; he walks bowed down until the hosts of the weak fall victim to his ways of violence.

He says to himself, "The LORD will never see our evil because I do not believe in His existence."

Arise LORD and by your Hand help the afflicted.

Why does the wicked person mock the LORD? He says in his heart, "The LORD does not care about us."

But You have seen this lawlessness; all things are in Your hands; You have been the helper of the orphan.

LORD, remove the wicked from the Earth so that You will not find it here anymore.

The LORD is King forever; however, the nations of the Earth will one day perish.

LORD, You have heard the desire of the humble; now guide their hearts and hear their cries for help.

Champion the orphans and the oppressed so that the men of violence will not continue to spread their terror around the Earth.

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

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